

***SOME PROBLEMS OF ADVANCED MATERIALS USED IN AEROSPACE ENGINEERING**

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ABSTRACT

The experiments of ablation process of C/C composite materials are carried out with the star type alternate current arc heater in this paper. The ablation results are analyzed using the on-line spectrum diagnoses of ablation process of C/C composite materials. The microstructure evolution rules and the ablation mechanism are investigated through SEM and TEM observation. Then a superficial ablative model and volumetric ablative model are set up for the C/C composite materials. Numerical simulation of ablation process is given simultaneously and is compared with the experimental one. It shows a good agreement.

KEYWORDS: Thermal protective composite, Micromechanics, Ablation, Ultra-high temperature

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites such as C/C composites are widely used in the aerospace industry. Investigation of ablation processes of composite materials plays an important role in many applied fields, in particular for designing a heat shield of re-entry vehicles. Historically, investigation of these materials has been driven by application-oriented materials needs, not the quest for fundamental understanding. However, the thermal and chemical stability of thermal protection materials present a variety of unique scientific challenges related to processing, characterization, and evaluation of performance. For example, basic research on thermal protection materials is needed to improve the understanding of microstructure evolution, provide insight into the mechanisms by which materials respond to high temperature reactive environments, and to promote the development of new testing methodologies that may be unique to the thermal protection materials. The CORIA center in France has developed three types of plasma simulation equipments^[1-3]. The characteristic spectrums of ablation results of thermal protective composites in the flow field of ground simulation system were measured and the observed results provided important evidences for the research of materials ablation mechanism^[4]. The ablation processes are usually divided into superficial and volumetric ablation. Superficial ablation causes decreasing geometrical dimensions of the structures, but volumetric ablation is a physico-chemical processes, which leads to decrease in density due to internal gas generation.

2. ABLATIVE EXPERIMENTS OF C/C COMPOSITES

2.1 Experiments with star type alternate current arc heater

At first, the ablative process of C/C composites is simulated with the star type alternate

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current arc heater. The work parameters of the star type alternate current arc heater can be adjusted broadly to suit the needed range. Detail parameters: the power 0.1-10MW, voltage 6-10KV, march number 2-3, used gas (air, N₂). Then the on-line emission spectrum diagnoses system of thermal protective materials was set up for the measure of ablative results. The C/C composite materials and the high module graphite are selected in the experiments. The ablative specimen is the cylindrical shape with the diameter 15mm (Fig.1). The enthalpy, heat flow, pressure, temperature and the ablation results are measured in the ablative process.

With the photoelectric pyrometer and the thermal couple the temperatures are measured on the ablative surface and in the interior. It can be clearly seen in Fig.2 that the stagnation temperatures after 20s is almost same between the two materials. The results of the line ablative recession are listed in the Table.1.

Fig.1 Ablative specimens of Graphite and C/C materials Fig.2 Temperature variation process of ablation plane

Table 1 the ablative quantity of two materials

	Graphite	C/C
original length (mm)	56.7	55.5
after ablative length (mm)	35.4	43.7
total ablative (mm)	21.3	11.8

The spectrum of ablative results including CN、C2、C1 and CO is given as seen in the Fig.3. It can be observed that mostly ablative results are CO but sublime results of carbon and CN are little.

Fig.3 Spectrum of C/C ablated in plasma of arc heater

We measure the density of different positions along the specimen axes and calculate the

relative void rate. The results of volumetric ablation in quantity are obtained. The result of the density and relative void rate at the sample position (in Fig.4) is listed in Table 2.

Fig.4 Sample taking position

Table 2 Distribution of material density and relative void rate

	Graphite		C/C	
	ρ_1	γ_1	ρ_2	γ_2
4	1.7403	1.78	1.9348	1.43
3	1.7530	1.07	1.9565	0.30
2	1.7696	0.13	1.9605	0.09
1	1.7719	0.00	1.9623	0.00

2.2 The ablative pattern of C/C composite materials

The instrument Talyscan150 is used to measure the ablative parameter. It can measure the ablative pattern of 2D and 3D. The stagnation pressure is 0.163 MPa, the enthalpy is 25.8MJ/kg. The ablative pattern is given in Fig.5. The roughness curve is given in Fig.6.

Fig.5 Ablative pattern of C/C composite material

Fig.6 Roughness curve of the C/C composite material

The ablations of Z-direction fibre and the XY cloth have a little difference from the roughness curve. The averaged increment of heat flux due to the variation of roughness is little. Compared to the XY cloth, the Z-direction fibre is higher than the matrix, approximately less than 20 μ m. The phenomenon shows that the interface is first ablated. The

result is agreed to the following ones from SEM of three dimension C/C composites.

2.3 SEM and TEM of ablation material

The observation from SEM indicates that the shape of Z-direction fibre is cusped on the head. Carbon fibre is a little high than carbon matrix on the ablative surface. There obviously exists gap between the fibre and the matrix. This tells us that the interface is ablated firstly. The SEM picture of Z-direction and XY direction composite are given in the Fig.6 and Fig.7. It demonstrates that the shape at the top of fibre becomes taper, and the surface of the fibre is smooth.

Fig.7 Z-direction SEM picture

Fig.8 XY direction SEM picture

The observation from TEM indicates the graphite becomes soft and deforms and forms the shape of canister with approximated size of 100nm. The structure of cylinder in the matrix can be seen in Fig.9. The micrystal on the surface of the fibre becomes big and its shape is strip with a width almost above 10nm and a length several hundreds nm. There also exists a gap in interface region, which dimension can change from several nm to hundreds nm.(Fig.10). The observations above indicate that the properties of ablation-resistant of C/C composites improved greatly compared with the Graphite materials.

Fig.9 Carbon structure of cylinder

Fig.10 The stripe micrystal of the fibre region

3. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND NUMERICAL CALCULATION

3.1 Superficial Ablative Model of C/C Composites

It can be seen from pattern analysis of SEM the ablative surface is considerably irregular. A simplified geometrical model is established as seen in Fig.11 in order to predict the local flow field.

Fig 11 Diagrammatic sketch of flat current with rough elements

It is assumed that the relatively smooth wall surface has become a rough surface which shows the distribution of microstructure with regular sine wave after ablation. The specific form compressible N-S equation of the planar laminar current governing equation under rectangular coordinates is

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial E_v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial F_v}{\partial y} \quad (1)$$

where: $U = [\rho, \rho u, \rho v, e]^T$,

$E = [\rho u, \rho u^2 + p, \rho uv, (e + p)u]^T$

$F = [\rho v, \rho vu, \rho v^2 + p, (e + p)v]^T$,

$E_v = \left[0, \tau_{xx}, \tau_{xy}, u\tau_{xx} + v\tau_{xy} + \kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right]^T$

$F_v = \left[0, \tau_{yx}, \tau_{yy}, u\tau_{yx} + v\tau_{yy} + \kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right]^T$

ρ , p and e are gas density, pressure and total energy of unit volume, respectively. u and v are velocity component along x and y . With the aid of finite difference method, the distribution of heat current and pressure can be achieved on the surface of composites. The Harten-Yee numerical flux can be deduced in computation as follows:

$$E_{i+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} [E_i + E_{i+1} + J_{i+1/2}^{-1} R_{i+1/2} \Phi_{i+1/2}] \quad (2)$$

The specific discrete method and form can be seen in the literature [5,6]. The following figures illustrate the distribution of pressure and heat flow at tip of carbon fiber.

Fig 12 Pressure distribution on flat arc anterior border tip

Fig. 13 Heat flow distribution on flat arc at anterior border tip

Ablative process of C/C composites can be divided into the two stages of the oxidation and the sublimation. Ablative velocity is generally dominated by superficial chemical kinetics under lower temperature, whereas the ablative velocity is dominated by sublime diffusion above sublime temperature.

Chemical kinetics equation [7]:

$$\dot{m}_c = \alpha_{ch} (Y_{\bar{O},w})^n \quad (3)$$

Where $\alpha_{ch} = k_o \left(\frac{\bar{M}_w}{M_o} p_e \right)^n \exp\left(-\frac{E}{\hat{R}T_w}\right)$, $Y_{\bar{O}} = Y_o + Y_{O_2}$ the mass rate of oxygen

Superficial conservation theorem of mass during oxygen diffusion:

$$\tilde{J}_{k_w} + (\rho v)_w \tilde{c}_{k_w} = \dot{m}_s \tilde{c}_{k_s} \quad (4)$$

where k denotes the kth component, \tilde{J}_{k_w} is the diffusion flow rate of chemical element k on the wall surface; ρ is the gas density on the wall surface; v is the gas velocity on the wall surface; \tilde{c}_{k_w} is the mass density of element k on the wall surface; \dot{m}_s is the mass loss factor of solids on the wall surface and \tilde{c}_{k_s} is mass density of element k in mass loss of solids on the wall surface.

Conservation of energy on the material surface:

$$q_b = q_w - [\dot{m}_w h_w - \dot{m}_w h_c(s)] + a q_r - \varepsilon \sigma T_w^4 \quad (5)$$

Where q_b the heat flow into materials, q_w the convection heat from environment to the border of materials, $\dot{m}_w h_w$ the heat taken away by the border gas, $\dot{m}_w h_c(s)$ the heat taken away because of border mass decrease, $a q_r$ radiation heat from environment to the border, $\varepsilon \sigma T_w^4$ the radiation heat from border to the environment.

Thermal response of material surface is followed the traditional thermal conduction equation:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = K \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \quad (6)$$

The thermal chemical equilibrium equation and mass conservation equation of material surface are nonlinear equation sets and can be solved by quasi-Newton method. The thermal conduction equation can be resolved by finite difference method and ablation process regarding time can be obtained from iteration method. Ablative quantity is obtained and compared with experimental results as listed in Table 3. Under the same stagnation pressure, the heat flow and the ablative recession rate increase as the enthalpy increases.

Table 3 Comparison of ablative recession rate between numerical and experimental results

	Numerical (mm/s)	Experimental (mm/s)	Relative error
N1	0.0089	0.01	11%
N2	0.157	0.15	5%
N3	0.272	0.25	9%

3.2 Volumetric Ablative Model of C/C Composites

An ablative composite material is considered to be a multiphase system consisting of five phases, the geometrical shape of each the phase is a certain finite domain V_i . This domain is not static, i.e. it changes with time $V_i = V_i(t)$ under the action of high temperatures, even without the presence of deformations, where i=a (amorphous), b (polymer), l (crystalline), p (pyrolytic) and g (gas of pores). Supposing the volume of the representative cell is φ :

$$\varphi = \varphi_a + \varphi_b + \varphi_l + \varphi_p + \varphi_g \quad (7)$$

Here φ_i is the volumetric content of different phases.

Then one can derive the volumetric functions for the ablative composite materials:

$$\varphi_f(\theta, t) = (1 - \Gamma_f) \varphi_f^0 + \Gamma_f \varphi_f^0 \exp \int_0^t -\frac{J_f^0}{\rho_f} \exp\left[-\frac{E_{Af}}{R\theta(\tau)}\right] d\tau \quad (8)$$

$$\varphi_b(\theta, t) = \varphi_b^0 \exp \int_0^t -\frac{J_m^0}{\rho_b} \exp\left[-\frac{E_{Am}}{R\theta(\tau)}\right] d\tau \quad (9)$$

Here ρ_f, ρ_b are densities of the fibers and the polymer phases of the matrix. Γ_f is the gasification coefficient of the fibers, J_f, J_m are the rates of volumetric ablation of the fiber and matrix, they describe heat-mass transfer intensity in thermo destruction in accordance with Arrhenius's law. J_f^0 and J_m^0 are pre-exponential factors determined by experiments. E_{Am} and E_{Af} are their activation energy, respectively, R is universal gas constant. Applying the micro mechanics theory [8], we can obtain thermo-mechanical properties under high temperature.

The boundary condition is firstly obtained with the use of the superficial ablation model. The calculated stress distribution along X direction is shown in Fig.14. The maximum tension stress occurs at the top surface, and the region nearly under the top surface is compression stress. The region is easy to be damaged.

Fig. 14 Distribution profile of thermal stress along x direction

4. CONCLUSION

The ablative recession rate was obtained by the ablation experiments using the star type alternate current arc heater. The ablative results were obtained with the on-line emission spectrum diagnoses. The ablative mechanism is unclosed and the microstructure evolution rules are known. Two ablative models of the C/C composite materials are given. Numerical simulation is carried out and theoretical results showed a good agreement with the experimental.

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